

1 Ancient DNA from an extinct Mediterranean micromammal –
2 *Hypnomys morpheus* (Rodentia: Gliridae) – provides insight
3 into the biogeographic history of insular dormice
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6 **SHORT RUNNING TITLE: Ancient DNA of *Hypnomys morpheus***
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44 **KEYWORDS:** Endemic, Fossil, Island fauna, Mitochondrial DNA, Phylogeny

45 **Abstract**

46 The dormice (Gliridae) are a family of rodents represented by relatively few extant species,
47 though the family was much more species-rich during the Early Miocene. Intergeneric
48 phylogenetic relationships among glirids in some cases remain unresolved, despite extensive
49 molecular and morphological analyses. Uncertainty is greatest with respect to the
50 relationships among fossil taxa and how extinct lineages are related to modern species. The
51 fossil genus *Hypnomys* from the Balearic Islands (western Mediterranean Sea) includes the
52 Late Pleistocene-Holocene species *Hypnomys morpheus*, which has variously been considered
53 a close relative or subgenus of the extant *Eliomys*. In the present study, we sequenced ancient
54 mitochondrial DNA from *H. morpheus*, which suggests a sister relationship with the extant
55 members of *Eliomys*. In addition, the pairwise sequence variation between *Hypnomys* and
56 *Eliomys* is higher than that observed between congeneric glirid species (*e.g.*, many
57 *Graphiurus* spp.), which allows us to reject the hypothesis that *Hypnomys* is a subgenus of
58 *Eliomys*. Our molecular dating analyses suggest that *Hypnomys* and *Eliomys* diverged 13.67
59 million years ago (95% Highest Posterior Density [HPD]= 7.39–20.07). The relatively early
60 split between these genera together with the molar morphology of early representatives of
61 *Hypnomys* points to a Middle-Late Miocene origin from a continental glirid with a complex
62 molar pattern, such as *Vasseuromys* or a closely related genus.

63 1. INTRODUCTION

64 The dormice (Gliridae) are a family of rodents whose interspecific phylogenetic
65 relationships have been widely discussed. In some cases these remain unresolved despite
66 analyses using extensive molecular datasets (*e.g.*, Bentz & Montgelard, 1999; Montgelard,
67 Matthee, & Robinson, 2003; Nunome, Yasuda, Sato, Vogel, & Suzuki, 2007) or
68 morphological characters (*e.g.*, Freudenthal & Martín-Suárez, 2013; Storch, 1995; Wahlert,
69 Sawitzke, & Holden, 1993). Within extant Gliridae, Holden (2005) recognises three
70 subfamilies: Graphiurinae (single genus *Graphiurus* Smuts, 1832, including three subgenera
71 and 15 species), Glirinae (monotypic genera *Glis* Brisson, 1762 and *Glirulus* Thomas, 1906),
72 and Leithiinae (including *Chaetocauda* Wang, 1985, *Dryomys* Thomas, 1906, *Eliomys*
73 Wagner, 1840, *Muscardinus* Kaup, 1829, *Myomimus* Ognev, 1924, and *Selevinia* Belosludov
74 and Bashanov, 1939, with a total of 12 species). A number of glirids have been recorded in
75 the Pliocene-Holocene fossil record of the Mediterranean Islands (van der Geer, Lyras, de
76 Vos, & Dermitzakis, 2010) several of which have been assigned to the subfamily Leithiinae
77 based on morphological characters, including the genus *Hypnomys* Bate, 1918 from the
78 Balearic Islands. However, the phylogenetic relationships of these extinct dormice have not
79 been tested using molecular data, which may provide new evidence to clarify uncertainties
80 about their taxonomy and biogeographical origin.

81 The extinct genus *Hypnomys* (Rodentia: Gliridae) was originally erected by Bate
82 (1918) to accommodate two species of Pleistocene dormouse discovered in the Balearic
83 Islands: *H. mahonensis* Bate, 1918 and *H. morpheus* Bate, 1918. de Bruijn (1966) initially
84 described an additional species — *H. gollcheri* — from the Pleistocene of Malta, though *H.*
85 *gollcheri* was ultimately transferred to the newly erected genus *Maltamys* Zammit-Maempel
86 and de Bruijn, 1982 (see Zammit-Maempel & de Bruijn, 1982). Similarly, while Esu and
87 Kotsakis (1980) recorded putative *Hypnomys* remains in the Early Pleistocene deposit of
88 Nuraghe Su Casteddu (Sardinia), this material was later included in *Tyrrhenoglis* Engesser,
89 1976, an endemic genus from Sardinia (Zammit-Maempel & de Bruijn, 1982). Alcover and
90 Agustí (1985) mentioned remains of a species of Gliridae from Cova de ca na Reia on Eivissa
91 (Pityusic Islands, western Group of the Balearic Islands; presumably from the Lower
92 Pleistocene/Upper Pliocene) that has often been considered to belong to *Hypnomys*, but this
93 material has never been properly studied.

94 According to Wahlert et al. (1993), members of the subfamily Leithiinae share four
95 morphological characters: posterior emargination or a foramen in the posterior part of the
96 squamosal bone, fenestra in the angle of the mandible, low inclination of the coronoid process
97 relative to the occlusal surface, and one complete transverse valley in the second lower molar.
98 *Hypnomys* possess all of these diagnostic morphological characters (Figure S1), though the
99 fenestra in the angle of mandible is not strictly present in all *Hypnomys* — or other Leithiinae
100 such as *Eliomys* — but in most of them (see Yuste & Calzada, 2009, and pers. obs.). More
101 specifically, a close relationship with *Eliomys* was suggested in the original description of
102 *Hypnomys* (Bate, 1918), on the basis of the general plan of the skull, mandible, and limb
103 bones, and a fenestra in the angle of the mandible. Subsequent studies also suggested that the
104 closest relative of *Hypnomys* was *Eliomys* (Petronio, 1970), *Leithia* Lydekker, 1895 (Mills,
105 1976), or *Tyrrhenoglis* (Chaline & Mein, 1979). Several authors have since suggested that the
106 Western Mediterranean insular fossil glirids — *Hypnomys*, *Leithia*, *Tyrrhenoglis*, *Maltamys*
107 and *Eivissia* Alcover and Agustí, 1985 — all descended from *Eliomys* (Alcover & Agustí,
108 1985; Alcover, Moyà-Solà, & Pons-Moyà, 1981; Daams & de Bruijn, 1995; Zammit-
109 Maempel & de Bruijn, 1982). Indeed, Agustí (1980) suggested that *Eliomys* should be
110 considered the most likely ancestor of *Hypnomys*, and Zammit-Maempel and de Bruijn (1982)
111 considered *Hypnomys* (and other insular genera as *Tyrrhenoglis* and *Maltamys*) as a subgenus
112 of *Eliomys*, which is a view that has been widely adopted in the literature (e.g., Alcover &
113 Agustí, 1985; Reumer, 1982, 1994). However, no consensus exists regarding the taxonomy of
114 these fossil glirid taxa.

115 Though it has never been directly tested, it is generally assumed that the ancestor of
116 *Hypnomys* likely dispersed to the Balearic Islands while they were connected by land to the
117 European mainland during the Late Miocene Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC) (e.g., Agustí,
118 1980, 1986; Alcover et al., 1981; Bover et al., 2014; Mas et al., 2018; Moyà-Solà & Pons-
119 Moyà, 1980). The fossil record in Mallorca is consistent with this biogeographical hypothesis,
120 with extensive evidence that a radiation of this endemic clade had occurred by the Pliocene:
121 *Hypnomys/Eliomys* sp. [Early Pliocene (Bover et al., 2014)], *Hypnomys* sp. [Zanclean (Bover
122 et al., 2014)], *H. waldreni* [Piazenician (Reumer, 1979)], *H. onicensis* [formerly *H.*
123 *intermedius*, Early Pleistocene (Reumer, 1981, 1994)], and *H. morpheus* [Middle Pleistocene-
124 Holocene Bate, 1918)]. Establishing the age of the divergence between this Mallorcan
125 dormouse lineage and its nearest living continental relatives may help in narrowing down its

126 phylogenetic origins by constraining the range of fossil taxa from which it could possibly
127 have descended.

128 Ancient DNA sequences have been successfully used for phylogenetic analyses of
129 small extinct species (see review in Woods, Marr, Brace, & Barnes, 2017) and can provide
130 information about phylogenetic relationships in situations that are challenging for
131 morphological analyses (*e.g.*, fossil insular species where taxonomic position is frequently
132 obscured by autapomorphies acquired during isolation). Although a close relationship
133 between *Hypnomys* and *Eliomys* based on morphology has been widely accepted, major
134 discrepancies in the attribution of several genera to different Gliridae subfamilies using
135 morphological (*e.g.*, Daams & de Bruijn, 1995; Freudenthal & Martín-Suárez, 2013; Storch,
136 1995; Wahlert et al., 1993) or molecular characters (*e.g.*, Bentz & Montgelard, 1999; Fabre,
137 Hautier, Dimitrov, & Douzery, 2012; Montgelard et al., 2003; Nunome et al., 2007) suggest
138 that the taxonomic position of *Hypnomys* requires confirmation using genetic data. In this
139 paper we generate the first DNA sequences for *Hypnomys* and use these to infer its
140 phylogenetic relationship to extant glirids. We also conduct molecular dating analysis to test
141 hypotheses about the biogeographic history of *Hypnomys* — specifically that the temporal
142 origin of the *Hypnomys* lineage coincides with the Messinian Salinity Crisis — and to identify
143 potential ancestral taxa in the fossil record.

144

145 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

146 **2.1. Samples**

147 In this study we attempted to extract DNA from four *Hypnomys morpheus* samples
148 curated at the vertebrate public collection of the Mediterranean Institute for Advanced Studies
149 (IMEDEA, Balearic Islands, Spain), and from three different caves (Figure 1): a pool of two
150 bones [left (ACAD 13111) and right (ACAD 13155) mandibles from Cova Estreta (Pollença)
151 (Encinas & Alcover, 1997)], a right mandible (ACAD 13307) from Cova de sa Bassa Blanca
152 (Alcúdia) (Ginés & Ginés, 1974), and a left tibia (ACAD 14874) from Coveta des Gorgs
153 (Escorca). The exact chronology of these samples could not be established as the specimens
154 were entirely consumed during DNA extraction and could not be radiocarbon dated.
155 Nevertheless, up to three radiocarbon dates have been obtained from remains obtained in the
156 same stratigraphic level of Cova Estreta: *H. morpheus* bone [UtC-5175, 6357±44 BP, 5469–
157 5288 (86.3%) 5272–5227 (9.1%) calBC,] (Encinas & Alcover, 1997), and a bone [UtC-5171,

158 5720±60 BP, 4716–4449 calBC,] (Encinas & Alcover, 1997) and coprolite [Wk-33010,
159 4950±38 BP, 3798–3650 calBC,] (Rivera et al., 2014) of the extinct bovid *Myotragus*
160 *balearicus* Bate, 1909. Radiocarbon dates of several bones of *M. balearicus* from the same
161 level (surface) of the Coveta des Gorgs indicate a chronology range from 4456±33 BP
162 [RICH-21771, 3339–3205 (45.2%) 3197–3014 (50.2%) calBC] to 9164±42 BP [RICH-21974,
163 8533–8516 (2.5%) 8480–8285 (92.9%) calBC] (Bover & Alcover, 2003; Bover et al., 2016,
164 2018; Lalueza-Fox, Shapiro, Bover, Alcover, & Bertranpetit, 2002). No chronology was
165 available for the sample from Cova de sa Bassa Blanca. Although several rodents are
166 currently living in Mallorca, differences in size and anatomy between them and *Hypnomys* are
167 distinctive enough to clearly discriminate genera in terms of dental, skull, and postcranial
168 morphology (Agustí, 1980; Bover, Alcover, Michaux, Hautier, & Hutterer, 2010; Mills, 1976;
169 Reumer, 1979, 1981, 1982). Up to six rodents currently live on the island as a result of
170 historical introductions (e.g., Alcover, 2010; Bover & Alcover, 2008), including the glirid
171 *Eliomys quercinus* (Linnaeus, 1766), and murids *Mus musculus* Linnaeus, 1758, *Mus spretus*
172 Lataste, 1883, *Apodemus sylvaticus* Linnaeus, 1758, *Rattus rattus* Linnaeus, 1758, and *Rattus*
173 *norvegicus* Berkenhout, 1769. The first human settlers to the island (around 4,300 years ago,
174 Bover et al., 2016) introduced *E. quercinus* and *A. sylvaticus*, which were putatively involved
175 in the extinction of the only pre-human rodent *H. morpheus* (Bover & Alcover, 2008). The
176 only *H. morpheus* sample that yielded endogenous DNA, tibia ACAD 14874 (see below,
177 sections 2.2 and 3), displays enough diagnostic traits to identify it as unquestionably
178 belonging to the fossil species: the cross-section of the distal half of the diaphysis and the
179 extent of the tibia-ulna synostosis allow the discrimination of Gliridae from Muridae tibiae. In
180 addition, the position and relative size of the trochlear process of the calcaneum and thus its
181 corresponding structure in the tibia are as in other glirids and not expanded distally as in
182 murids (Stains, 1959), and the lateral groove of the tibia resembles that of *Eliomys*, not
183 weakly developed as in murids (Mills, 1976). However, differences in size between the
184 Mallorcan *E. quercinus* and *H. morpheus* allow each to be discriminated from the other
185 (Bover et al., 2010). The tibiae of *H. morpheus* have been illustrated by Alcover and Roca
186 (1975), Alcover et al. (1981) and Bover et al. (2010).

187

188 (FIGURE 1 HERE)

189

190 **2.2. Extraction, library preparation, enrichment and sequencing**

191 Sample processing, DNA extraction, PCR preparation, and library construction were
192 performed at the facilities of the Australian Centre for Ancient DNA (ACAD) at the
193 University of Adelaide (Australia). The samples were cleaned with surgical blades to remove
194 surface contamination and dirt, irradiated with UV for 30 min on each side, wiped with 3%
195 sodium hypochlorite, soaked for 2 min in 80% ethanol to fully remove sodium hypochlorite,
196 air-dried, and finally irradiated again for 15 min on each side. Each sample was placed in a
197 sterilised stainless steel container with an 8 mm tungsten ball and powdered using a Braun
198 Mikrodismembrator U (B. Braun Biotech International, Berlin, Germany) for 5 s at 3000 rpm.
199 We obtained 190 mg for the pool of ACAD 13111 and 13155, 150 mg of bone powder for
200 sample ACAD 13307, and 180 mg for sample ACAD 14874. The bone powder for each
201 sample was decalcified and digested overnight at 55 °C on a rotary wheel in 4 ml 0.5M EDTA
202 (pH 8.0) (Life Technologies, Carlsbad, CA, USA), 200 µl of 10 % SDS (Life Technologies),
203 and 40 µl of 20 mg/ml Proteinase K (Life Technologies). DNA extraction was performed
204 using a modified QG buffer [15.5 mL QG buffer (Qiagen, Valencia, CA, USA), 1.3 % Triton
205 X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA), 25 mM NaCl (Sigma-Aldrich), 0.17 M
206 Sodium Acetate (Sigma-Aldrich)] and suspended in 100 µl of silicon dioxide solution
207 (Brotherton et al., 2013). Samples were then purified using 80 % ethanol and bound DNA was
208 eluted in 200 µl TLE buffer (10mM Tris, 0.1mM EDTA, pH 8). A negative control was
209 included for all extractions. No other glirids have ever been processed in the ancient DNA
210 laboratory at ACAD before.

211 A PCR reaction was performed to screen for the presence of DNA using primer pairs
212 Mamm_12S_E and Mammal_12S_H (Macqueen, Seddon, Austin, Hamilton, & Goldizen,
213 2010) to amplify a ~ 95 bp fragment of mitochondrial *12S ribosomal RNA* gene (*12S*). Two
214 microlitres of template were used in the PCR reaction (final volume 25 µl), which contained:
215 1 × Platinum Taq High Fidelity Buffer (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA), 3 mM MgSO₄, 0.4
216 µM each primer, 0.25 mM each dNTP, 1.25 U Platinum Taq HiFi (Invitrogen), 2 mg/ml
217 Rabbit Serum Albumin (RSA, Sigma-Aldrich). PCR cycling conditions were: initial
218 denaturation at 94 °C for 2 min; 50 cycles of denaturation at 94 °C for 20 seconds (s), primer
219 annealing at 55 °C for 15 s, elongation at 68 °C for 30 s; and a final elongation step at 68 °C
220 for 10 min. PCR products were visualized under UV light on a 3.5 % agarose gel stained with
221 Gel-Red (Jomar Bioscience, Kensington, Australia). PCR products were purified using

222 Agencourt AMPure XP magnetic beads (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA, USA) according to the
223 manufacturer's protocol. Both strands were sequenced using the BigDye 3.1 Terminator Kit
224 (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). Dye terminators were removed using the
225 Agencourt CleanSEQ magnetic particle solution (Beckman Coulter) and DNA sequencing
226 was performed on 3130xl and 3730xl Genetic Analyzers (Applied Biosystems).

227 Of the three *H. morpheus* samples analysed, only ACAD 14874 (Coveta des Gorgs)
228 yielded a positive PCR amplification. Sanger sequencing of the purified amplicon from
229 ACAD 14874 produced a 95 bp fragment after primer trimming. The first BLASTn (Altschul
230 et al., 1997) hit of this sequence against the NCBI nucleotide database (accessed 10-January-
231 2019) was the garden dormouse *Eliomys quercinus* (Coverage 98%, Identity 95%, E-value 6e-
232 32), whereas a second hit was the Asian garden dormouse *Eliomys melanurus* (Wagner, 1840)
233 (Coverage 100%, Identity 93%, E-value 4e-29).

234 We constructed a double-stranded DNA sequencing library from ACAD 14874
235 following the protocol described by Meyer and Kircher (2010) using modifications as in
236 Llamas et al. (2016), which uses truncated Illumina adapters with a P5 5-mer barcode and
237 Platinum Taq HiFi (Invitrogen) for post-*Bst* amplification. Enrichment of this library for
238 mtDNA was performed using the protocol described by Mitchell et al. (2016). We performed
239 two parallel enrichment reactions of the DNA library. Following amplification with full-
240 length Illumina sequencing adapters, the molecules retained after enrichment were sequenced
241 on an Illumina HiSeq (Fast Run 2x100 PE), an Illumina MiSeq (2x150 PE), and a NextSeq
242 (2x75 PE) runs.

244 **2.3. Sequencing data processing and sequence assembly**

245 Resulting reads were demultiplexed according to P5 barcode sequences using Sabre
246 v.1.0 (<https://github.com/najoshi/sabre>) allowing one mismatch (option -m 1), adapter
247 sequences were removed using AdapterRemoval v.2.1.7 (Schubert, Lindgreen, & Orlando,
248 2016) and paired reads were collapsed in a single read when overlapping by 11 nucleotides. A
249 concatenated file of 2,136,646 collapsed reads from the three sequencing runs was used to
250 iteratively map to different references. To date (April 2019) the only available complete
251 mitochondrial genomes from glirids available in GenBank are from *Glis glis* (Linnaeus, 1766)
252 and *Graphiurus kelleni* (Reuvens, 1890), and in general, mitochondrial sequences for the
253 Gliridae is scarce, with *cytochrome b* (*CYTB*) and *12S* genes as the most represented genes

254 across the family. For this reason we mapped our sequencing reads to the putatively closest
255 relative of *Hypnomys*, *Glis glis* (complete mitochondrial genome, GenBank accession number
256 NC_001892), and the longest available *CYTB* and *12S* sequences for genus *Eliomys* (*E.*
257 *quercinus*: *CYTB* Accession number GQ453668, *12S* Accession number Y16896; *E.*
258 *melanurus*: *CYTB* assembly of sequences HE614010 and KF422705, *12S* Accession number
259 AJ536350; see Table 1 for details on references and mapping results) using BWA v.0.7.17 (Li
260 & Durbin, 2009) with the recommended parameters for ancient DNA (aln -l 1024, -n 0.01, -o
261 2). Reads with a mapping quality Phred score above 25 were filtered using SAMtools v.1.8
262 (Li et al., 2009), and duplicates removed using FilterUniqueSAMCons.py (Kircher, 2012).
263 Mapping results were visualised using Geneious v.11.1.4 (Biomatters,
264 <http://www.geneious.com>, Kears e et al., 2012), with 75% majority intermediate consensus
265 sequences generated in Geneious using the reference to call nucleotides in positions with
266 coverage read-depth < 3. This consensus was then used as reference for a new round of
267 mapping. The process was iterated until no more unique reads were mapped to the reference.
268 We generated final 75% majority consensus sequences with nucleotides only called in
269 positions with coverage read-depth $\geq 3x$. Nucleotide misincorporation and DNA fragmentation
270 patterns were assessed using mapDamage v.2.0.2 (Jónsson, Ginolhac, Schubert, Johnson, &
271 Orlando, 2013).

272

273 (TABLE 1 HERE)

274

275 We recovered up to 3,501 bp of the *Hypnomys morpheus* mitochondrial genome after
276 18 mapping iterations to *Glis glis* mitogenome (Table 1), including nine complete *transfer*
277 *RNA* genes [*Cysteine (Cys)*, *Glutamine (Gln)*, *Glutamic acid (Glu)*, *Isoleucine (Ile)*, two
278 *Leucines (Leu1, Leu 2)*, *Methionine (Met)*, *Tyrosine (Tyr)*, *Valine (Val)*], fragments of six
279 protein coding genes [*NADH dehydrogenase subunit 1 (ND1)* (65 bp, two fragments), *NADH*
280 *dehydrogenase subunit 2 (ND2)* (17 bp, one fragment), *NADH dehydrogenase subunit 5*
281 *(ND5)* (40 bp, one fragment), *NADH dehydrogenase subunit 6 (ND6)* (43 bp, one fragment),
282 *cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COXI)* (259 bp, two fragments), and *cytochrome b (CYTB)*
283 (318 bp, one fragment)], and fragments of the two *rRNA* genes [*12S* (697 bp, four fragments)
284 and *16S ribosomal RNA (16S)* (1,221 bp, five fragments)]. Sequences obtained for *12S* and
285 *CYTB* genes were aligned to the corresponding sequences from the iterative mapping to

286 isolated *I2S* and *CYTB* genes of *Eliomys quercinus* (942 and 361 bp of each gene recovered,
287 respectively) and *E. melanurus* (848 and 590 bp of each gene recovered, respectively). The
288 sequences for each gene overlapped and were identical, and thus, the longest sequence for
289 each gene were selected for the phylogenetic analysis. Despite the low number of unique
290 reads mapping to each reference, mapDamage analyses (Figure S2) displayed damage
291 patterns consistent with ancient samples for unrepaired libraries (Briggs et al., 2007).

292

293 **2.4. Phylogenetic analyses**

294 We aligned the *Hypnomys morpheus I2S* (942 bp, GenBank Accession Number
295 MN153772) and *CYTB* (590 bp, GenBank Accession Number MN164630) sequences with
296 available data from other glirid and outgroup species (Table 2 for GenBank Accession
297 Numbers) using MUSCLE (Edgar, 2004) in Geneious. We adjusted the size of each gene in
298 all the 18 species to the length of these genes obtained for *H. morpheus*, and ambiguous
299 regions in the *I2S* gene alignment were removed using stringent default parameters in
300 Gblocks v.0.91b (Castresana, 2000), which kept 739 out of the 1,014 bp of the full *I2S*
301 alignment (73%). Our final alignment (see Alignment S1 in Supporting Information)
302 comprised 1,330 bp (591 bp for *CYTB* and 739 bp for *I2S*). Partitioning schemes and
303 substitution models (Table 3) in the *I2S* region and codon positions in the *CYTB* region were
304 estimated in PartitionFinder v.2.1.1 (Lanfear, Frandsen, Wright, Senfeld, & Calcott, 2016).
305 We inferred a Maximum Likelihood tree in RAxML v.8.2.11 (Stamatakis, 2014), with node
306 support values estimated by performing 1000 bootstrap replicates. We also performed a
307 MrBayes v.3.2.3 analysis (Ronquist et al., 2012) with four separate runs of four Markov
308 chains each using default priors. Each chain ran for 10⁸ generations sampling trees and
309 parameter values every 10⁴ generations. Sampled trees were summarized as a majority-rule
310 consensus tree after discarding the first 10 % of trees as burnin (Figure S3).

311

312 (TABLE 2 HERE)

313

314 We implemented a birth-death tree prior and a single relaxed uncorrelated lognormal
315 clock model (with rate multipliers for each of the three partitions, see Table 3) to estimate
316 phylogeny and divergence times using BEAST v.1.8.4 (Drummond, Suchard, Xie, &
317 Rambaut, 2012). To calibrate our analysis, we followed previous studies (e.g., Montgelard et

318 al., 2003; Nunome et al., 2007; Mouton et al., 2017) and constrained the age of the divergence
319 between Sciuridae and Gliridae according to a uniform distribution with a minimum of 50
320 million years ago (Mya) and a maximum of 55 Mya, corresponding to the earliest known
321 fossil representatives of these families (Hartenberger, 1998). We repeated our analysis four
322 times with different starting trees created using Mesquite v.3.04 (Maddison & Maddison,
323 2018) based on an ML tree created using IQTREE v.1.6.6 (Nguyen, Schmidt, von Haeseler, &
324 Minh, 2015). Each analysis comprised a chain of 10^8 iterations, sampling every 10^4 iterations.
325 Parameter convergence and sampling was assessed using Tracer v.1.6.1. The first 10 % of
326 trees from each chain were removed as burn-in, with the remainder from each chain combined
327 using LogCombiner v.1.8.4 and summarised using TreeAnnotator v.1.8.4 (Rambaut &
328 Drummond, 2010).

329

330 (TABLE 3 HERE)

331

332 We graphically depicted the pairwise distances between different Gliridae sequences
333 using the heatmap similarity (%) implemented in Geneious (Figure S4) for the two different
334 mitochondrial genes available (16 species for the *12S* gene and nine for the *CYTB* and a
335 combination of *CYTB* and *12S*).

336 We tested the position of *Hypnomys morpheus* in relation to the variation within the
337 *Eliomys* genus using a 370-bp *CYTB* fragment obtained for 48 individuals of *E. quercinus*
338 (Accession numbers AJ225030, FM164278, FR848957, FR848958, GQ453668, GQ453669,
339 HE611090-HE611093, HE613976-HE614008, JX457812-JX457816), eight individuals of *E.*
340 *melanurus* (Accession numbers FM164279, FM164280, FR848955, FR848956, HE614009-
341 HE614012), and *Graphiurus kelleni* (Accession number HE978360) as outgroup using an
342 unpartitioned IQTREE analysis. The same alignment without the outgroup was used in the
343 haplotype network analysis using Fitchi (Matschiner, 2015). *Eliomys* clades obtained in both
344 IQTREE and Fitchi analyses (Figure S5) has been named following Perez, Libois, and
345 Nieberding (2013).

346

347 **3. RESULTS**

348 The mapDamage analysis (Figure S2), which shows the expected damage pattern of
349 degraded ancient DNA, and negative PCR results on both extraction blank controls and other

350 extracts from *Hypnomys* samples rule out the possibility of any introduction of contaminants
351 or cross-contamination during lab work.

352 Overall, the results of our phylogenetic analyses are consistent with the published molecular
353 phylogenies of Gliridae (*e.g.*, Fabre et al., 2012; Montgelard et al., 2003; Nunome et al.,
354 2007). While we did not find strong support for the previously established *Glis-Glirulus*
355 clade, our results agree with Holden (2005)'s classification of glirid subfamilies —
356 Graphiurinae (including *Graphiurus*), Glirinae (including *Glis* and *Glirulus*), and Leithiinae
357 (including *Eliomys*, *Dryomys*, *Muscardinus*, and *Myomimus*) — which we find to be
358 reciprocally monophyletic. Both Maximum-Likelihood (ML) and MrBayes Bayesian
359 Inference (BI) analyses supported the monophyly of Graphiurinae (Maximum Likelihood
360 bootstrap value [MLB]= 100, Posterior Probability [PP] = 1) and Leithiinae (*sensu* Holden,
361 2005; MLB = 79, PP = 0.99, Figure S3). The monophyly of the Leithiinae node has been
362 previously well supported just using a 952 bp fragment of the *12S* by Montgelard et al.
363 (2003). However, our results do not recapitulate support for Glirinae (*Glis-Glirulus* node) or
364 the basal position of *Muscardinus* and *Myomimus* within Leithiinae, which were observed in
365 published molecular phylogenies based on nuclear genes or a combination of nuclear and
366 mitochondrial genes (Fabre et al., 2012; Montgelard et al., 2003; Nunome et al., 2007).
367 Importantly, we obtained high support for a clade comprising *Hypnomys morpheus* and
368 *Eliomys* (MLB = 100, PP = 1), and for the monophyly of *Eliomys* (MLB = 100, PP = 1) and
369 *Dryomys* (MLB = 99, PP = 1). The clade formed by these three genera (*Dryomys*, *Eliomys*,
370 *Hypnomys*) received moderate support (MLB = 78, PP = 0.95).

371 The time-calibrated tree (Figure 2) displayed a similar topology to the uncalibrated
372 Bayesian tree, *i.e.*, monophyly with similarly high posterior probability values of clades
373 Gliridae (PP = 1), Graphiurinae (PP = 1), Leithiinae (PP = 1), *Dryomys* (PP = 1), and *Eliomys*
374 (PP = 1), a *Hypnomys-Eliomys* clade (PP = 1), and a *Dryomys-Hypnomys-Eliomys* clade (PP =
375 0.97). The main difference between the trees was the unresolved relationship of Glirinae with
376 Leithiinae (PP = 0.68, uncalibrated tree) or with Graphiurinae (PP = 0.49, calibrated tree). In
377 general, the 95% Highest Posterior Densities (HPD) of node ages were wide, though they
378 overlapped with those observed in previously published glirid phylogenies (Table 4). The split
379 between the fossil *Hypnomys* and its putative sister taxon *Eliomys* was 13.67 Mya (95% HPD
380 = 7.39–20.07).

381

382 (FIGURE 2 AND TABLE 4 HERE)

383

384 Our ML analysis using only the 370 bp *CYTB* sequences of *Eliomys*, *Hypnomys*
385 *morpheus*, and the outgroup *Graphiurus kelleni* (Figure S5.b) resulted in moderate support for
386 the monophyly of *Eliomys* (MLB = 88) with *H. morpheus* as its sister-taxon. Our haplotype
387 network (Figure S5.a) further illustrates the distinction between *H. morpheus* and extant
388 *Eliomys* variation. Both analyses indicated that sequences from the fossil *H. morpheus* do not
389 fall within the variability of the modern *E. quercinus* and *E. melanurus*. As expected, pairwise
390 comparisons of sequence similarity displayed higher values when species from the same
391 genus were analysed (Figure S4). For the 591 bp of *CYTB*, similarity values > 93% and >
392 90% were observed between congeneric species within *Eliomys* and *Graphiurus*, respectively.
393 For this same *CYTB* fragment *H. morpheus* displayed a similarity of 84% and 85% with *E.*
394 *quercinus* and *E. melanurus*, respectively, comparable to the similarity values observed
395 between members of other glirid genera e.g. *Muscardinus-Glis* (85.2%), *Glirulus-Glis*
396 (84.2%), or *Graphiurus kelleni-Glis* (84%). Similar patterns were observed in our pairwise
397 analysis of the 739 bp of the *I2S* gene. The highest similarity values were displayed by
398 pairwise comparison between congeneric species within *Eliomys* (96.6 %), *Dryomys* (95.4%),
399 and *Graphiurus* (93-99.6%). Values around 93% were also observed for pairwise comparison
400 between *Hypnomys-E. quercinus* (93.8%), *Hypnomys-E. melanurus* (93.1%), and *Glirulus-*
401 *Glis* (93.5%). Finally, where data were available for both *CYTB* and *I2S*, the highest values
402 were again observed between congeneric species within *Eliomys* (95.2%) and *Graphiurus*
403 (93%), followed by *Hypnomys-E. quercinus* (89.4%), *Hypnomys-E. melanurus* (89.5%), and
404 *Glirulus-Glis* (89.4%).

405 Our phylogenetic analyses clearly places our *H. morpheus* within Gliridae and as sister
406 clade of *Eliomys* (Figures 2 and S3). For this reason, we can confidently discard the
407 hypothesis that the tibia belongs to a murid, especially to similar-sized rodents of the genus
408 *Rattus* Fischer de Waldheim, 1803. Furthermore, the position of *H. morpheus* sequences
409 outside the genetic variability of *Eliomys CYTB* gene (Figure S5), clearly shows that there is
410 no reason to interpret our data as a result of a misidentification of an *Eliomys* bone.

411

412 **4. DISCUSSION**

413 Our molecular data are fully consistent with a close relationship between *Hypnomys*
414 and *Eliomys*, as suggested by past morphological analyses (e.g., Agustí, 1980, 1981; Bate,
415 1918; Mills, 1976; Zammit-Maempel & de Bruijn, 1982). The basal placement of *H.*
416 *morpheus* outside the variability of the modern *Eliomys* species and the pairwise similarity
417 (Figure S4) between the fossil and each of two *Eliomys* species studied here (which display
418 equivalent levels of similarity as that between *Glis* and *Glirulus*; but see *Graphiurus platyops*
419 Thomas, 1897 in comparison with other *Graphiurus* species using *12S* data) suggest that
420 *Hypnomys* should not be considered as a subgenus of *Eliomys*, and the generic status
421 established by Bate (1918) should be retained.

422 In general, the lowest values of the 95% HPD intervals for node ages (Table 4) are
423 similar to the values obtained by Nunome et al. (2007) whereas the highest values of 95%
424 HPD intervals are similar to those obtained by Montgelard et al. (2003). However,
425 Freudenthal and Martín-Suárez (2013) suggested that the base age of Gliridae (50 Mya) used
426 as a calibration age by Montgelard et al. (2003) was too old and should be replaced by 16
427 Mya, a view that has subsequently not been followed (e.g., Mouton et al., 2017). Despite the
428 uncertainties of the node ages of our (and other published) calibrated trees, the available
429 *Hypnomys-Eliomys* divergence estimate of 13.67 Mya (95% HPD = 7.39–20.07 Mya) allows
430 us to identify three possible palaeobiogeographic scenarios for the origin of the *Hypnomys*
431 lineage in the Balearic Islands.

432 The first possible origin for *Hypnomys*, which is the most commonly accepted
433 hypothesis (e.g., Agustí, 1980; Alcover et al., 1981; Bover et al., 2014; Colom, 1978; Mas et
434 al., 2018; Moyà-Solà & Pons-Moyà, 1980) involves a split from a continental ancestor during
435 the Late Tortonian/Early Messinian (Figure 2) and its arrival into the Balearic Islands during
436 the Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC, 5.97–5.33 Mya; Krijgsman, Hilgen, Raffi, Sierro, &
437 Wilson, 1999; Manzi et al., 2013). According to Agustí (1986) and Bover, Quintana, and
438 Alcover (2008) the putative continental ancestor would be the fossil species *Eliomys*
439 *intermedius* Priant, 1953 or *E. truci* Mein and Michaux, 1970, both representatives of the
440 lineage *E. truci-E. yevesi-E. intermedius-E. quercinus* (Mansino, García-Álix, Ruiz-Sánchez,
441 & Montoya, 2015). However, preliminary morphological analysis of the earliest known
442 representative of the *Hypnomys* lineage (currently under analysis) obtained from the Early
443 Pliocene Zanclean site of Na Burguesa-1 (NB-1) on Mallorca conflicts with this hypothesis.
444 The NB-1 glirid shows an unexpectedly complex dental pattern (Figure 3), whereas proposals

445 that *Hypnomys* descends from fossil *Eliomys* species (e.g. Agustí, 1980, 1981, 1986; Alcover
446 & Agustí, 1985; Bate, 1918; Zammit-Maempel & de Bruijn, 1982) suggest that members of
447 the *Hypnomys* lineage evolved increasing dental pattern complexity through time from a
448 relatively dentally simple *Eliomys*-like ancestor. Reumer (1982) likewise observed a contrary
449 trend towards a simplification of the dental pattern in the *Hypnomys* lineage (from *H.*
450 *waldreni* to *H. morpheus*). Thus, while the results of our molecular dating analyses are
451 consistent with this hypothesis, it conflicts with available morphological evidence.

452

453 (FIGURE 3 HERE)

454

455 An alternative and more morphologically plausible origin for *Hypnomys* is its descent
456 from a Middle-Late Miocene glirid with a high dental complexity, such as *Vasseuromys*
457 Baudelot and de Bonis, 1966, or some closely related genus. *Vasseuromys* spans the latest
458 Oligocene to Late Miocene (Sinitza & Nesin, 2018) while the older *Microdyromys* de Bruijn,
459 1966 and *Bransatoglis* Hugueneu, 1967, which also possess high dental complexity, span the
460 Early Oligocene to the Middle Miocene and the Late Oligocene to the Middle Miocene,
461 respectively (Freudenthal & Martín-Suárez, 2013). Under this scenario, the simplified dental
462 pattern displayed by more recent *Hypnomys* species (Figure 3) would be an effect of insular
463 evolution (Reumer, 1982).

464 A final possibility for the origin of *Hypnomys*, consistent with the upper bounds of our
465 node age 95% HPDs, is an early split from mainland ancestors and pre-MS-C arrival to the
466 Balearic Islands during the Langhian-Serravalian regression (Moyà-Solà, Quintana, Alcover,
467 & Köhler, 1999; Riba, 1981). However, the fossil record of mammals of this age from
468 Mallorca and Menorca is restricted to the ochotonid *Gymnesicolagus gelaberti* Mein and
469 Adrover, 1982, and the glirids *Carbomys sacaresi* Mein and Adrover, 1982, *Margaritamys*
470 *llulli* Mein and Adrover, 1982 and *Peridyromys ordinasi* Mein and Adrover, 1982 in Mallorca
471 (Adrover, Agustí, Moyà-Solà, & Pons-Moyà, 1985; Mein & Adrover, 1982), and
472 *Margaritamys adroveri* Quintana and Agustí, 2007 in Menorca (Quintana & Agustí, 2007).
473 All of the glirids from this faunal episode have lower dental complexity than NB-1 glirid,
474 making them unlikely ancestors (as for *Eliomys*).

475 Although the resolving of phylogenetic relationships of all extinct and extant Gliridae
476 subfamilies is beyond the scope of this paper, the dental morphology and the genetics of

477 *Hypnomys* clearly supports its inclusion within Leithiinae. Our node age estimates, the
478 chronological range of *Vasseuromys*, and the original complex dental pattern of *Hypnomys*
479 (see Figure 3.a in this paper, and *Vasseuromys tectus* Sinista and Nesin, 2018 depicted in
480 Figure 6 in Sinista & Nesin, 2018) suggest that *Vasseuromys*, or some close relative, could be
481 considered as the potential ancestor of *Hypnomys*.

482 Ultimately, obtaining additional genetic data from extinct and extant dormouse species
483 as well as a systematic review of extinct genera could contribute to further illuminating the
484 evolution, taxonomy, and palaeobiogeography of Gliridae.

485

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493

494 **REFERENCES**

- 495 Adrover, R., Agustí, J., Moyà-Solà, S., & Pons-Moyà, J. (1985). Nueva localidad con
496 micromamíferos insulares del Mioceno medio en las proximidades de San Lorenzo en la
497 isla de Mallorca. *Paleontologia i Evolució*, 18, 121–130.
- 498 Agustí, J. (1980). *Hypnomys eliomyoides* nov. sp., nuevo glírido (Rodentia, Mammalia) del
499 Pleistoceno de Menorca (Islas Baleares). *Endins*, 7, 49–52.
- 500 Agustí, J. (1981). Cladistics and paleomastology: Application to the phylogeny of rodents. I:
501 Neogene gliridae from Europe. In J. Martinell (Ed.), *International Symposium: Concept
502 and method in paleontology* (pp. 103–110). Barcelona: Universitat de Barcelona.
- 503 Agustí, J. (1986). Dental evolution in the endemic glirids of the Western Mediterranean
504 Islands. In D. E. Russell, J. -P. Santoro & D. Sigogneau-Russell, D. (Eds.), *Teeth revisited:
505 Proceedings of the VIIth International Symposium on Dental Morphology, Paris 1986.
506 Mémoires du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle. Série C*, 53, 227–232.
- 507 Alcover, J. A. (2010). Introduccions de mamífers a les Balears: l'establiment d'un nou ordre.
508 In C. Álvarez Pola (Ed.), *Seminari sobre espècies introduïdes i invasores a les Illes
509 Balears* (pp. 175–186). Sóller: Conselleria de Medi Ambient i Mobilitat.
- 510 Alcover, J. A., & Agustí, J. (1985). *Eliomys (Eivissia) canarreiensis* n. sgen., n. sp., nou glírid
511 del Pleistocè de la Cova de ca na Reia (Pitiüses). *Endins*, 10-11, 51–56.
- 512 Alcover, J. A., & Roca, L. (1975). Noves aportacions al coneixement del gènere *Hypnomys*
513 Bate 1918 i els seus jaciments. *Speleon*, 22, 81–102.
- 514 Alcover, J. A., Moyà-Solà, S., & Pons-Moyà, J. (1981). *Les quimeres del passat. Els
515 vertebrats fòssils del Plio-Quaternari de les Balears i Pitiüses*. Palma de Mallorca:
516 Editorial Moll.
- 517 Altschul, S. F., Madden, T. L., Schäffer, A. A., Zhang, J., Zhang, Z., Miller, W., & Lipman,
518 D. J. (1997). Gapped BLAST and PSI-BLAST: a new generation of protein database
519 search programs. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 25, 3389–3402.
520 <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/25.17.3389>
- 521 Bate, D. M. A. (1918). On a new genus of extinct muscardine rodent from the Balearic
522 Islands. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London*, 1918, 209–222.
523 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1096-3642.1918.tb02091.x>

- 524 Bentz, S., & Montgelard, C. (1999). Systematic position of the African dormouse *Graphiurus*
525 (Rodentia, Gliridae) assessed from Cytochrome b and 12S rRNA mitochondrial genes.
526 *Journal of Mammalian Evolution*, 6, 67–83. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020590430250>
- 527 Bover, P., & Alcover, J. A. (2003). Understanding Late Quaternary extinctions: the case of
528 *Myotragus balearicus* (Bate, 1909). *Journal of Biogeography*, 30, 771–781.
529 <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2699.2003.00872.x>
- 530 Bover, P., & Alcover, J. A. (2008). Extinction of the autochthonous small mammals of
531 Mallorca (Gymnesic Islands, Western Mediterranean) and its ecological consequences.
532 *Journal of Biogeography*, 35, 1112–1122. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2007.01839.x)
533 [2699.2007.01839.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2007.01839.x)
- 534 Bover, P., Alcover, J. A., Michaux, J. J., Hautier, L., & Hutterer, R. (2010). Body shape and
535 life style of the extinct Balearic dormouse *Hypnomys* (Rodentia, Gliridae): new evidence
536 from the study of associated skeletons. *PLoS ONE*, 5, e15817.
537 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0015817>
- 538 Bover, P., Quintana, J., & Alcover, J. A. (2008). Three islands, three worlds: paleogeography
539 and evolution of the vertebrate fauna from the Balearic Islands. *Quaternary International*,
540 182, 135–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2007.06.039>
- 541 Bover, P., Mitchell, K. J., Llamas, B., Rofes, J., Thomson, V. A., Cuenca-Bescós, G., ... Pons,
542 J. (2018). Molecular phylogenetics supports the origin of an endemic Balearic shrew
543 lineage (*Nesiotites*) coincident with the Messinian Salinity Crisis. *Molecular Phylogenetics*
544 *and Evolution*, 125, 188–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2018.03.028>
- 545 Bover, P., Rofes, J., Bailón, S., Agustí, J., Cuenca-Bescós, G., Torres, E., & Alcover, J. A.
546 (2014). The Late Miocene/Early Pliocene vertebrate fauna from Mallorca (Balearic
547 Islands, Western Mediterranean): an update. *Integrative Zoology*, 9, 183–196.
548 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1749-4877.12049>
- 549 Bover, P., Valenzuela, A., Torres, E., Cooper, A., Pons, J., & Alcover, J. A. (2016). Closing
550 the gap: new data on the last documented *Myotragus* and the first human evidence on
551 Mallorca (Balearic Islands, Western Mediterranean Sea). *Holocene*, 26, 1887–1891.
552 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683616645945>
- 553 Briggs, A. W., Stenzel, U., Johnson, P. L. F., Green, R. E., Kelso, J., Prüfer, K., ... Pääbo, S.
554 (2007). Patterns of damage in genomic DNA sequences from a Neandertal. *Proceedings of*

555 *the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 104, 14616–14621.
556 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0704665104>

557 Brotherton, P., Haak, W., Templeton, J., Brandt, G., Soubrier, J., Adler, C. J., ... The
558 Genographic Consortium. (2013). Neolithic mitochondrial haplogroup H genomes and the
559 genetic origin of Europeans. *Nature Communications*, 4, 1764.
560 <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms2656>

561 Castresana, J. (2000). Selection of conserved blocks from multiple alignments for their use in
562 phylogenetic analysis. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 17, 540–552.
563 <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.molbev.a026334>

564 Chaline, J., & Mein, P. (1979). *Les rongeurs et l'évolution*. Paris: Doin Éditeurs.

565 Colom, G. (1978). *Biogeografía de las Baleares. Tomo I y II* (2nd ed.). Palma de Mallorca:
566 Estudio General Luliano.

567 Daams, R., & de Bruijn, H. (1995). A classification of the Gliridae (Rodentia) on the basis of
568 dental morphology. *Hystrix*, 6, 3–50. <https://doi.org/10.4404/hystrix-6.1-2-4015>

569 de Bruijn, H. (1966). On the Pleistocene Gliridae (Mammalia, Rodentia) from Malta and
570 Mallorca. *Proceedings of the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen*
571 *Series B*, 69, 480–496.

572 Drummond, A. J., Suchard, M. A., Xie, D., & Rambaut, A. (2012). Bayesian phylogenetics
573 with BEAUti and the BEAST 1.7. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 29, 1969–1973.
574 <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/mss075>

575 Edgar, R. C. (2004). MUSCLE: multiple sequence alignment with high accuracy and high
576 throughput. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 32, 1792–1797. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkh340>

577 Encinas, J. A., & Alcover, J. A. (1997). El jaciment fòssilífer de la Cova Estreta (Pollença).
578 *Endins*, 21, 83–92.

579 Esu, M., & Kotsakis, T. (1980). Presenza di *Hypnomys* (Gliridae, Rodentia) nel
580 Villafranchiano di Nuraghe Su Casteddu (Nuoro, Sardegna). *Rendiconti della Accademia*
581 *Nazionale dei Lincei*, 68, 123–127.

582 Fabre, P. H., Hautier, L., Dimitrov, D., & Douzery, E. J. P. (2012). A glimpse on the pattern
583 of rodent diversification: a phylogenetic approach. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 12, 88.
584 <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2148-12-88>

585 Freudenthal, M., & Martín-Suárez, E. (2013). New ideas on the systematics of Gliridae
586 (Rodentia, Mammalia). *Spanish Journal of Palaeontology*, 28, 239–252.

587 Ginés, A., & Ginés, J. (1974). Consideraciones sobre los mecanismos de fosilización de la
588 Cova de sa Bassa Blanca y su paralelismo con formaciones marinas del Cuaternario.
589 *Bolletí de la Societat d'Història Natural de les Balears*, 19, 11–28.

590 Hartenberger, J. L. (1998). Description de la radiation des Rodentia (Mammalia) du
591 Paléocène supérieur au Miocène; incidences phylogénétiques. *Comptes Rendus de*
592 *l'Académie des Sciences. Series IIA: Earth and Planetary Science*, 326, 439–444.
593 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1251-8050\(98\)80068-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1251-8050(98)80068-2)

594 Holden, M. E. (2005). Family Gliridae. In D. E. Wilson & D. M. Reeder (Eds.), *Mammal*
595 *species of the World. A taxonomic and geographic reference* (3rd ed.)(pp. 819–841).
596 Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.

597 Jónsson, H., Ginolhac, A., Schubert, M., Johnson, P., & Orlando, L. (2013). mapDamage 2.0:
598 fast approximate Bayesian estimates of ancient DNA damage parameters. *Bioinformatics*,
599 29, 1682–1684. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btt193>

600 Kearse, M., Moir, R., Wilson, A., Stones-Havas, S., Cheung, M., Sturrock, S., ... Drummond,
601 A. (2012). Geneious Basic: an integrated and extendable desktop software platform for the
602 organization and analysis of sequence data. *Bioinformatics*, 28, 1647–1649.
603 <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bts199>

604 Kircher, M. (2012). Analysis of high-throughput ancient DNA sequencing data. *Methods in*
605 *Molecular Biology*, 840, 197–228. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-61779-516-9_23

606 Krijgsman, W., Hilgen, F. J., Raffi, I., Sierro, F. J., & Wilson, D. S. (1999). Chronology,
607 causes and progression of the Messinian Salinity Crisis. *Nature*, 400, 652–655.
608 <https://doi.org/10.1038/23231>

609 Lalueza-Fox, C., Shapiro, B., Bover, P., Alcover, J. A., & Bertranpetit, J. (2002). Molecular
610 phylogeny and evolution of the extinct bovid *Myotragus balearicus*. *Molecular*
611 *Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 25, 501–510. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1055-7903\(02\)00290-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1055-7903(02)00290-7)
612 7

613 Lanfear, R., Frandsen, P. B., Wright, A. M., Senfeld, T., & Calcott, B. (2016). PartitionFinder
614 2: new methods for selecting partitioned models of evolution for molecular and
615 morphological phylogenetic analyses. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 34, 772–773.
616 <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msw260>

617 Li, H., & Durbin, R. (2009). Fast and accurate short read alignment with Burrows Wheeler
618 transform. *Bioinformatics*, 25, 1754–1760. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btp698>

619 Li, H., Handsaker, B., Wysoker, A., Fennell, T., Ruan, J., Homer, N., ... 1000 Genome Project
620 Data Processing Subgroup. (2009). The Sequence alignment/map (SAM) format and
621 SAMtools. *Bioinformatics*, 25, 2078–2079. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btp352>

622 Llamas, B., Fehren-Schmitz, L., Valverde, G., Soubrier, J., Mallick, S., Rohland, N., ... Haak,
623 W. (2016). Ancient mitochondrial DNA provides high-resolution time scale of the peopling
624 of the Americas. *Science Advances*, 2, e1501385. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1501385>

625 Macqueen, P., Seddon, J. M., Austin, J. J., Hamilton, S., & Goldizen, A. W. (2010).
626 Phylogenetics of the pademelons (Macropodidae: Thylogale) and historical biogeography
627 of the Australo-Papuan region. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 57, 1134–1148.
628 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2010.08.010>

629 Maddison, W. P., & Maddison, D. R. (2018). Mesquite: a modular system for evolutionary
630 analysis. Version 3.51 [software]. <http://www.mesquiteproject.org>.

631 Mansino, S., García-Álix, A., Ruiz-Sánchez, F. J., & Montoya, P. (2015). A new *Eliomys*
632 from the Late Miocene of Spain and its implications for the phylogeny of the genus. *Acta*
633 *Palaeontologica Polonica*, 60, 577–588. <https://doi.org/10.4202/app.00014.2013>

634 Manzi, V., Gennari, R., Hilgen, F., Krijgsman, W., Lugli, S., Roveri, M., & Sierro, F. J.
635 (2013). Age refinement of the Messinian salinity crisis onset in the Mediterranean. *Terra*
636 *Nova*, 25, 315–327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ter.12038>

637 Mas, G., Maillard, A., Alcover, J. A., Fornós, J. J., Bover, P., & Torres-Roig, E. (2018).
638 Terrestrial colonization of the Balearic Islands: new evidence for the Mediterranean sea-
639 level drawdown during the Messinian Salinity Crisis. *Geology*, 46, 527–530.
640 <https://doi.org/10.1130/G40260.1>

641 Matschiner, M. (2015). Fitchi: Haplotype genealogy graphs based on the Fitch algorithm.
642 *Bioinformatics*, 32, 1250–1252. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btv717>

643 Mein, P., & Adrover, R. (1982). Une faunule de mammifères insulaires dans le Miocène
644 moyen de Majorque (Iles Baléares). *Geobios*, 6, 405–463. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-6995(82)80133-2)
645 [6995\(82\)80133-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-6995(82)80133-2)

646 Meyer, M., & Kircher, M. (2010). Illumina sequencing library preparation for highly
647 multiplexed target capture and sequencing. *Cold Spring Harbor Protocols*, 2010, 1–10.
648 <https://doi.org/10.1101/pdb.prot5448>

649 Mills, D. H. (1976). *Osteological study of the Pleistocene dormouse Hypnomys morpheus*
650 *Bate from Mallorca (Rodentia, Gliridae). Publications from the Palaeontological*
651 *Institution of the University of Uppsala, Special Volume 4.* Uppsala: University of Uppsala.

652 Mitchell, K. J., Bray, S. C., Bover, P., Soibelzon, L., Schubert, B. W., Prevosti, F., ... Cooper,
653 A. (2016). Ancient mitochondrial DNA reveals convergent evolution of giant short-faced
654 bears (Tremarctinae) in North and South America. *Biology Letters*, 12, 20160062.
655 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2016.0062>

656 Montgelard, C., Matthee, C. A., & Robinson, T. J. (2003). Molecular systematics of dormice
657 (Rodentia: Gliridae) and the radiation of *Graphiurus* in Africa. *Proceedings of the Royal*
658 *Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences*, 270, 1947–1955.
659 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2003.2458>

660 Mouton, A., Grill, A., Sara, M., Krystufek, B., Randi, E., Amori, G., ... Michaux, J. (2012).
661 Evidence of a complex phylogeographic structure in the common dormouse, *Muscardinus*
662 *avellanarius* (Rodentia: Gliridae). *Biological Journal of the Linnan Society of London*, 15,
663 648–664. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8312.2011.01807.x>

664 Mouton, A., Mortelliti, A., Grill, A., Sara, M., Krystufek, B., Juskaitis, R., ... Michaux, J. R.
665 (2017). Evolutionary history and species delimitations: a case study of the hazel dormouse,
666 *Muscardinus avellanarius*. *Conservation Genetics*, 18, 181–196.
667 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10592-016-0892-8>

668 Moyà-Solà, S., Quintana, J., Alcover, J.A., & Köhler, M. (1999). Endemic island faunas of the
669 Mediterranean Miocene. In K. Heissig & G. Rössner (Eds.), *The Miocene mammals of*
670 *Europe* (pp. 435–442). München: Verlag Dr. Friedrich Pfell.

671 Moyà-Solà, S., & Pons-Moyà, J. (1980). Una nueva especie del género *Myotragus* Bate, 1909
672 (Mammalia, Bovidae) en la isla de Menorca: *Myotragus binigausensis* nov. sp..
673 implicaciones paleozoogeográficas. *Endins*, 7, 37–47.

674 Nguyen, L. T., Schmidt, H. A., von Haeseler, A., & Minh, B. Q. (2015). IQ-TREE: a fast and
675 effective stochastic algorithm for estimating Maximum-Likelihood phylogenies. *Molecular*
676 *Biology and Evolution*, 32, 268–274. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msu300>

677 Nunome, M., Yasuda, S. P., Sato, J. J., Vogel, P., & Suzuki, H. (2007). Phylogenetic
678 relationships and divergence times among dormice (Rodentia, Gliridae) based on three
679 nuclear genes. *Zoologica Scripta*, 36, 537–546. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1463-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1463-6409.2007.00296.x)
680 [6409.2007.00296.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1463-6409.2007.00296.x)

681 Perez, G. C. L., Libois, R., & Nieberding, C. M. (2013). Phylogeography of the garden
682 dormouse *Eliomys quercinus* in the western Palearctic region. *Journal of Mammalogy*, 94,
683 202–217. <https://doi.org/10.1644/11-MAMM-A-404.1>

684 Petronio, C. (1970). I roditori pleistocenici della grotta di Spinagallo. *Geologica Romana*, 9,
685 144–194.

686 Quintana, J., & Agustí, J. (2007). Los mamíferos insulares del Mioceno medio y superior de
687 Menorca (Islas Baleares, Mediterráneo occidental). *Geobios*, 40, 677–687.
688 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geobios.2006.11.007>

689 Rambaut, A., & Drummond, A. J. (2010). TreeAnnotator version 1.6.1 [software].
690 <http://beast.bio.ed.ac.uk>.

691 Reumer, J. W. F. (1979). On two new micromammals from the Pleistocene of Mallorca.
692 *Proceedings of the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen. Series B*, 82,
693 473–482.

694 Reumer, J. W. F. (1981). The Pleistocene small mammals from Sa Pedrera de s'Ònix,
695 Majorca (Gliridae, Soricidae). *Proceedings of the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van*
696 *Wetenschappen. Series B*, 84, 3–11.

697 Reumer, J. W. F. (1982). Some remarks on the fossil vertebrates from Menorca, Spain.
698 *Proceedings of the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen. Series B*, 85,
699 77–87.

700 Reumer, J. W. F. (1994). *Eliomys (Hypnomys) onicensis* nomen novum to replace the
701 homonym *Hypnomys intermedius* Reumer, 1981 (Rodentia: Gliridae) from Majorca.
702 *Zeitschrift für Säugetierkunde*, 9, 380–381.

703 Riba, O. (1981). Aspectes de la geologia marina de la conca mediterrània balear durant el
704 Neògen. *Memòries de la Reial Acadèmia de Ciències i Arts de Barcelona*, 45, 1–115.

705 Rivera, L., Baraza, E., Alcover, J. A., Bover, P., Rovira, C. M., & Bartolomé, J. (2014).
706 Stomatal density and stomatal index of fossil *Buxus* from coprolites of extinct *Myotragus*
707 *balearicus* Bate (Artiodactyla, Caprinae) as evidence of increased CO₂ concentration
708 during the late Holocene. *Holocene*, 24, 876–880.
709 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683614530445>

710 Ronquist, F., Teslenko, M., van der Mark, P., Ayres, D. L., Darling, A., Höhna, S., ...
711 Huelsenbeck, J. P. (2012). MrBayes 3.2: Efficient Bayesian phylogenetic inference and
712 model choice across a large model space. *Systematic Biology*, 61, 539–542.

713 <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/sys029>.

714 Schubert, M., Lindgreen, S., & Orlando, L. (2016). AdapterRemoval v2: rapid adapter
715 trimming, identification, and read merging. *BMC Research Notes*, 12, 88.
716 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-016-1900-2>

717 Sinitsa, M. V., & Nesin, V. A. (2018). Systematics and phylogeny of *Vasseuromys*
718 (Mammalia, Rodentia, Gliridae) with a description of a new species from the late Miocene
719 of Eastern Europe. *Palaeontology*, 61, 679–701. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pala.12359>

720 Stains, H. J. (1959). Use of the calcaneum in studies of taxonomy and food habits. *Journal of*
721 *Mammalogy*, 40, 392–401. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1376564>

722 Stamatakis, A. (2014). RAxML version 8: a tool for phylogenetic and post-analysis of large
723 phylogenies. *Bioinformatics*, 30, 1312–1313. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu033>

724 Storch, G. (1995). Affinities among living dormouse genera. *Hystrix*, 6, 51–62.
725 <https://doi.org/10.4404/hystrix-6.1-2-4016>

726 van der Geer, A., Lyras, G., de Vos, J., & Dermitzakis, M. (2010). *Evolution of island*
727 *mammals. Adaptation and extinction of placental mammals on islands*. Chichester: Wiley-
728 Blackwell.

729 Wahlert, J. H., Sawitzke, S. L., & Holden, M. E. (1993). Cranial anatomy and relationships of
730 dormice (Rodentia, Myoxidae). *American Museum Novitates*, 3061, 1–32.

731 Woods, R., Marr, M. M., Brace, S., & Barnes, I. (2017). The small and the dead: a review of
732 ancient DNA studies analysing micromammal species. *Genes*, 8, 312.
733 <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes8110312>

734 Yuste, C. S., & Calzada, J. (2009). Ausencia de orificio en la apófisis angular de la mandíbula
735 del lirón careto *Eliomys quercinus* (Linnaeus, 1766). *Galemys*, 21, 31–37.

736 Zammit-Maempel, G., & de Bruijn, H. (1982). The Plio/Pleistocene Gliridae from the
737 Mediterranean islands reconsidered. *Proceedings of the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie*
738 *van Wetenschappen. Series B*, 85, 113–128.

739 **Figure legends**

740

741 **FIGURE 1.** Map showing the location of Mallorcan deposits with respective *Hypnomys*
742 *morpheus* bones used for ancient DNA analysis. ACAD 13111, left mandible. ACAD 13155,
743 right mandible. ACAD13307, right mandible. ACAD 14874, left tibia. Mandibles ACAD
744 13111 and 13155 were pooled for DNA extraction. The asterisk indicates the sample that
745 yielded endogenous DNA.

746

747 **FIGURE 2.** Phylogenetic position of *Hypnomys morpheus* within Gliridae based on
748 mitochondrial sequences (1,330 bp) and using BEAST. Nodes are labelled with Bayesian
749 posterior probabilities (PP), and circles in nodes indicate PP=1. Purple bars represent 95%
750 highest posterior density (HPD) intervals. Possible colonization events during the Langhian-
751 Serravalian Regression (LSR) and Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC) are indicated by gray
752 shadings. See Table 2 for information about individual samples and accession numbers.
753 PLIO: Pliocene; PLEI: Pleistocene. Time in million years before present (BP).

754

755 **FIGURE 3.** Decrease of complexity pattern in occlusal surface of teeth in the *Hypnomys*
756 phylogenetic lineage depicted using lower molars (m1-2) from different Mallorcan fossil
757 glirids. From least recent to more recent (a) Gliridae from Na Burguesa-1 (NB1), Zanclean
758 (Early Pliocene); (b) *H. onicensis* (Early Pleistocene); (c) *H. morpheus* (Middle Pleistocene to
759 Holocene).

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763

764 **List of Supporting Information**

765

766 Supplementary figures

767

768 **FIGURE S1.** *Hypnomys morpheus* bones showing the characters shared by Leithiinae
769 according to Wahlert et al. (1993). Skull in lateral view (a) and right mandible in lingual view
770 (b) of specimen CDC-2 (Bover et al., 2010), and occlusal view of second lower molar (c). 1=

771 foramen (or posterior emargination) in the posterior part of the squamosal bone; 2= fenestra in
772 the angle of the mandible; 3= low inclination of the coronoid process relative to the occlusal
773 surface; 4= one complete transverse valley in the second molar.

774

775 **FIGURE S2.** Results of mapDamage analyses of reads from *Hypnomys morpheus* mapped to
776 *Eliomys CYTB* and *I2S* genes and to *Glis glis* complete mitogenome (Accession numbers
777 provided in the figure). Substitution (4 top panels) and misincorporation (2 bottom panels)
778 panels display the pattern typically observed in ancient samples.

779

780 **FIGURE S3.** Maximum-Likelihood and Bayesian phylogenetic relationships of Gliridae (see
781 Table 2 for extant individuals and accession numbers) including the extinct *Hypnomys*
782 *morpheus* (ACAD 14874), and *Glaucomys volans* and *Sciurus vulgaris* as outgroups. The
783 analysis was performed in RAxML and MrBayes using 1,330 bp of mitochondrial *CYTB* and
784 *I2S* genes. Bootstrap values for ML (MLB) and Bayesian posterior probabilities (PP) are
785 given at left and right, respectively, of each node. Nodes with circles indicate MLB=100 and
786 PP=1. *Graphiurus* species have been collapsed in a single branch. *Muscardinus avellanarius*
787 and *Myomimus roachi* positions are reversed in the ML tree (shown by red dashed lines).

788

789 **FIGURE S4.** Heatmap of pairwise similarity between the Gliridae sequences used in this
790 paper. See Table 2 for accession numbers of the sequences used. As expected, intraspecific
791 similarity is higher than interspecific similarity (darkest gray and black squares). The
792 similarity level between *Hypnomys morpheus* sequences and the sister taxa *Eliomys* does not
793 support the inclusion of the fossil in the same genus.

794

795 **FIGURE S5.** Haplotype network analysis (a) and ML tree (b) of 370-bp fragment of *CYTB*
796 from 56 *Eliomys* individuals and *Hypnomys morpheus*. Bootstrap values in ML tree (b) are just
797 depicted for selected nodes. *Eliomys* clades named following Perez et al. (2013). Names and
798 symbols in gray indicate unknown locality for the specimen. The outgroup in ML tree (b),
799 *Graphiurus kelleni* HE978360, has been removed for graphical reasons. See Material and
800 Methods (section 2.4) for individuals and accession numbers. In both analyses it can be
801 observed that *H. morpheus* sequence widely departs from *Eliomys* variability.

802

803 **ALIGNMENT S1.** Alignment of 1,330 bp of *CYTB* and *12S* mitochondrial genes in Phylip
804 format used for the Gliridae phylogenetic analyses.

805 **TABLES**

806 **TABLE 1.** Reference information and iterative mapping results. Up to 2,136,646 sequencing reads from *Hypnomys morpheus* enriched libraries
 807 were mapped to the different sequences used as reference.

808

REFERENCE DATA				MAPPING RESULTS				
Species	Sequence	GenBank #	Length (bp)	Iterations	Unique reads	Coverage (%)	Coverage depth (x)	Mean Fragment length (bp)
<i>Glis glis</i>	Mitogenome	NC_001892	16,602	18	1,066	23.5	4.8	74.3
<i>Eliomys quercinus</i>	<i>CYTB</i>	GQ453668	1,140	14	143	33.3	9.2	73.0
<i>Eliomys quercinus</i>	<i>12S</i>	Y16896	963	5	314	99.7	24.2	74.0
<i>Eliomys melanurus</i>	<i>CYTB</i>	HE614010 + KF422705	1,003	13	197	61.8	15.0	76.7
<i>Eliomys melanurus</i>	<i>12S</i>	AJ536350	967	5	279	94.5	21.3	73.7

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811

812 **TABLE 2.** Gliridae and outgroup samples and accession numbers. Mitochondrial *12S* and *CYTB* sequences were used in the Maximum
 813 Likelihood and Bayesian Inference phylogenetic analyses.

Species	<i>12S</i>	<i>CYTB</i>
<i>Dryomys laniger</i> Felten and Storch, 1968	AJ536349	
<i>Dryomys nitedula</i> (Pallas, 1778)	D89005	KJ739702
<i>Eliomys melanurus</i> (Wagner, 1840)	AJ536350	HE614010 + KF422705
<i>Eliomys quercinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Y16896	AJ225030
<i>Glirulus japonicus</i> (Schinz, 1845)	D89007	D89001
<i>Glis glis</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	NC_001892	NC_001892
<i>Graphiurus kelleni</i> (Reuvens, 1890)	HE978360	HE978360
<i>Graphiurus lorraineus</i> Dollman, 1910	AJ536356	
<i>Graphiurus microtis</i> (Noack, 1887)	AJ536352	
<i>Graphiurus murinus</i> (Desmarest, 1822)	AJ536351	AJ225115
<i>Graphiurus ocellaris</i> (Smith, 1829)	AJ536355	
<i>Graphiurus parvus</i> (True, 1893)	AJ536353	
<i>Graphiurus platyops</i> Thomas, 1897	AJ536354	
<i>Muscardinus avellanarius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	D89006	AJ225117
<i>Myomimus roachi</i> (Bate, 1937)	AJ536348	
<i>Glaucomys volans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) (outgroup)	AF038020	AF157921
<i>Sciurus aestuans</i> Linnaeus, 1766 (outgroup)	AJ012746	AJ389530

815 **TABLE 3.** Optimal partitioning scheme inferred using PartitionFinder. The total alignment consists of 1,330 bp (591 bp for *CYTB* and 739 bp for
816 *12S*) from 19 Gliridae species. See Table 2 for accession number details.

817

818

Partition	Substitution model		
	RAxML	MrBayes	BEAST
<i>12S, CYTB_1</i>	GTR+G	GTR+G	GTR+G
<i>CYTB_2</i>	GTR+G	HKY+I	HKY+I
<i>CYTB_3</i>	GTR+G	HKY+G	HKY+G

819 **TABLE 4.** Divergence ages of selected nodes reported in this and previous studies. All ages are in millions of years ago.

820

Node	This paper	Montgelard et al., 2003	Nunome et al., 2007	Mouton et al., 2012	Mouton et al., 2017
<i>(E. quercinus, E. melanurus)</i>	1.91–8.19	7.0 ± 0.9	na	4.87-8.88	5.56-7.49
<i>(D. nitedula, D. laniger)</i>	3.85–15.96	16.7 ± 1.8	na	na	na
<i>(Eliomys, Dryomys)</i>	14.47–31.84	28.5 ± 2.8	14.5 ± 2.4	na	13.08-24.40
<i>((Eliomys, Dryomys), Myomimus)</i>	17.56–37.89	38.1 ± 3.6	na	na	na
Leithiinae	20.55–41.36	40.8 ± 3.8	22.3 ± 2.8	9.85-54.36	na
<i>(Glis, Glirulus)</i>	16.12–41.34	27.7 ± 3	27.0 ± 2.9	na	na
Graphiurinae	9.00–25.04	8.7 ± 1	na	na	na
Gliridae	26.91–50.08	50.0	28.6 ± 2.9	na	na
(Sciuridae, Gliridae)	50.00–54.72	na	52.7 ± 1.4	na	na

821

FIGURE 1. Map showing the location of Mallorcan deposits with respective *Hypnomys morpheus* bones used for ancient DNA analysis. ACAD 13111, left mandible. ACAD 13155, right mandible. ACAD13307, right mandible. ACAD 14874, left tibia. Mandibles ACAD 13111 and 13155 were pooled for DNA extraction. The asterisk indicates the sample that yielded endogenous DNA.

180x153mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIGURE 2. Phylogenetic position of *Hypnomys morpheus* within Gliridae based on mitochondrial sequences (1,330 bp) and using BEAST. Nodes are labelled with Bayesian posterior probabilities (PP), and circles in nodes indicate PP=1. Purple bars represent 95% highest posterior density (HPD) intervals. Possible colonization events during the Langhian-Serravalian Regression (LSR) and Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC) are indicated by gray shadings. See Table 2 for information about individual samples and accession numbers. PLIO: Pliocene; PLEI: Pleistocene. Time in million years before present (BP).

180x127mm (300 x 300 DPI)

FIGURE 3. Decrease of complexity pattern in occlusal surface of teeth in the *Hypnomys* phylogenetic lineage depicted using lower molars (m1-2) from different Mallorcan fossil glirids. From least recent to more recent (a) Gliridae from Na Burguesa-1 (NB1), Zanclean (Early Pliocene); (b) *Hypnomys onicensis* (Early Pleistocene); (c) *Hypnomys morpheus* (Middle Pleistocene to Holocene).

180x64mm (300 x 300 DPI)